

THEORY AND PRACTICE OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This work aims to show methodology of foreign teaching referred to the problem of relying on the native language. Interlink - a system of rules of the program belonging to their native language. In the future, this system of rules is increasingly reduced.

Key words: psychological point of view, indirect ownership, pho-kinetic-systems, social consciousness, an unbounded set of linguistic properties.

Today there is no need to prove that the 21st century is commonly acknowledged to be the century of globalization and vanishing borders, the century of information and communication technologies and the Internet, the century of ever growing competition worldwide and in the global market.

Indeed, it was impossible to provide the independent economy, social and political stability, and development of intellectual and spiritual potential of the nation without rebuilding the system of education and upbringing. The state policy in the field of education that could transform it into the priority sphere has been developed and conducted.

The problem of support in their native language is discussed in this article. Switching from one language to another, from a psychological point of view, it is in the most general case; change the rules of the transition from the program to implement it. This transition cannot of course be implemented immediately in a fundamental way that is by the simultaneous and simultaneous switching of the old rules to the new ones. A human being is not capable of speaking a foreign language

immediately. He must go through a stage of indirect ownership of a foreign language. Interlink - a system of rules of the program belonging to their native language. In the future, this system of rules is increasingly reduced.

We will talk about that in the methodology of foreign language teaching referred to the problem of relying on native language. We are used to this, unfortunately, that in the majority of works on the subject, it is reduced to the imposition of one language system to a system of a different language and analysis of distinct fragments. This is exactly the direction that's called comparative study of pho-kinetic-systems of the two languages. On the shortcomings of the work on the comparative grammar and phonetics in 1969, was written by N. Yartsev, we cannot agree with that. She pointed out that the majority of authors is limited to the formal description of the selected language, first in one language and then in the other, without raising the question of the functional significance of the grammatical phenomena of the studied language and place in the grammatical system of the language as a whole.

It has been said about the work of linguistic. However, the same is true in relation to the works, directed the language of instruction, can be easily seen by picking up at least the brochures of Babalova "On the specific features of the Russian language in comparison to English language" and Benaiah "On characteristic peculiarities of Russian language in comparison with French language", published in 1962 by the University of Peoples' Friendship named after Patrice Lumumba.

However, even marked elimination of Yartseva shortage, that is, an introduction to the comparative grammar and phonetics principles systematically, does not give us the required optimum. The fact that the results of a comparison of speech production itself useless for learning. Comparison for training purposes is therefore in comparison operations performed by us on different levels of awareness generation and speech analysis of their psycho-physical nature and location of the

conditionality-especially dominant peculiarities, the change of which the easiest way will lead us to the desired change in the results of these processes.

Switching from one language to another, from a psychological point of view, are in the most general case, change the rules of the transition from program and its implementation. This transition cannot of course be implemented immediately in a fundamental way, that is, by simultaneously and one-torque switching of the old to the new rules. A person cannot just speak in a foreign language. He has to go through various language skills. Interchanging link - a system of rules of the program, serving in their native language, this is more reduced in the future.

The end "point" of the process of simultaneous reduction of automation is to establish a direct link between program and rules of the language system, which corresponds to the full knowledge of foreign languages, ability to think in a foreign language.

The above-described support capabilities into the native language, in reality boil down to a specific pre-known algorithm of actions to ensure the best way of reduction those rules.

Language involves a set of tools for the expression of thought; in each separate individual case to select one of them. But the basis for selection is not often indicated. The first task of building a speech in foreign language is to take into account the actual circumstances the intended message and to correlate them with the target language grammatical forms. Thus, the practical task (find objective circumstances for a reasonable construction of the speech in a foreign language) makes it necessary to distinguish between two forms of social consciousness - cognitive and proper language, cognitive.

Language consciousness each lexical and especially grammatical category - a set of values for all of its forms, the representation-represented in natural languages is always a limited set and referring clearly to certain conditions of their use. The features of linguistic consciousness most clearly stands by comparing these values

in several languages, where the shapes of the same category have different meanings, as well as the comparison is always an oriented set of linguistic values with an unbounded set of linguistic properties and relations of the objects. In his speech as a special form of human actions reflects out of language howling actually serve the impact of the speaker to the listener. By virtue of this function, speech language values reflect the extra linguistic reality as follows:

- 1) Biased;
- 2) Specifying the circumstances that are legalized in the language and provides an unambiguous message.

Cognitive mind - the product of recognizing objects. The advantage of cognitive consciousness is realness which can be verified by practice.

In contrast to the cognitive linguistic consciousness it has developed as a means of joint activities. The advantage of language and in turn language awareness, check the efficiency of communication, the measure of coincidence behavior recipient so that the speaker expects from his posts. Language consciousness does not seek completeness of reality, but to a fundamental set of such means of communication, which the company established the conditions attached to certain characteristics of the object and provide the desired their understanding and proper implementation in verbal behavior.

Cognitive consciousness - cognitive images are reflected by the movement of things and are designed to serve the action with things. Channel knowledge Information images are senses and logical motion. The main characteristic of the images - the truth. Criteria - Practice as the harmonization of actual results to the fact that waiting for elk in accordance with the original ideas about things.

Language consciousness - a reflection of the interests and conditions of the Report, other people thought that is intended to serve the organization of joint activities and achieved by certain highlighting in the speech of the status quo, which should be considered listener, and it seems he does not know, or otherwise. Channels

of understanding the speech are not only senses and not just thinking how much empathy listener voice message, and for speakers the criterion of correctness of the chosen construction of speech are, respectively, the behavior of the recipient's target of verbal communication.

And speech and knowledge are subject to orientation. But regional orientation is different; even though the person is subject activity is always public, according to a joint organization. It helps listeners to decide on joint activities with the speaker and understanding in the focus of the object changes.

Linguistic forms, such as articles and different verb forms require taking into account when using not only the content of an objective concept, but the circumstances of his message. In addition, each set of natural language over the formal means, each of its categories takes into account only some circumstances in different languages are different. So, when choosing article for the noun in the English language must be aware of whether it is a single object (a table, a glass), whether it is known to the addressee, but to solve the problem of the article is not important category of gender, and in the Russian language is required be sure to specify the gender of a noun (a table, a glass) and the verb to agree with him. We move into different forms of the English verb. Infinitive form of the English verb meaning is not that the action was uncertain, but just the fact that the speaker is only interested in real time actions, and other characteristics of the verb go unheeded. Action is always a process, but continuous placed only in the case when the speaker wants to emphasize its procedural.

In short, even in these cases, relatively simple choice over-lying the formal structure of language is dictated not so much the subject content plan, as the circumstances of the speech, which must take into account the speaker. To do this, you must first imagine a whole set of forms used by the grammatical category, to clarify their meaning (in the circumstances that involves each of them), and then an example of how these values actually correspond to the intended stances verbal

expression. The discrepancy between the values of formal structures, the language of signs and representations of concepts and subject content design appears especially clear in cases where the situation is even more complicated than in the case of products and differences of English verb forms.

The subject matter of design is out of the language: speaking in Russian, we do not think that a table or a glass - "man", although considering it, what to say about them "it" would be wrong not only from the point of view-of grammar, but also logic, since there is no thought without language, and in the Russian language kind of nouns and adjectives is an important indication of the relationship of words in a sentence, provides one-atomicity speech processing thoughts. Without such a voice combination it is thought losing the certainty of its content. The actual values of linguistic extra linguistic content conceived by rage-not only in thought, that is, on its substantive content, but also historically established requirements of univocally of language and verbal communication, its expression and understood.

A known amount of the properties can be identified in the action, but every natural language defines and represents only some of them and lowers other properties. It is impossible to replenish species of Russian verb forms in English and vice versa.

And yet, most importantly, of course, not in the numerical limitation of properties, celebrated the language, and not in the fact that the content they are also somewhat different than properties that are found in the same facilities of scientific thinking. The main thing is that in the language of these properties natural merge with characteristics very different plan - general-governmental relations. Such a merger properties with different nature is considerably and the public - in the sciences of the objects themselves. A language is a special form of human action serves as a means of influence of the speaker on the listener. The peculiarity of this influence is that it is carried out not physically but through the message about things

is their image that makes listener to understand these things, generates a certain attitude towards them.

Of course, language is not fixed one-off and standard of circumstance-verbal communication of the people speaking this language.

And, of course, that the particular historical development of each language leads to the fact that the messages in different languages are allocated different characteristics. For example, in English and Russian point of view on the essential characteristics of the different actions. And on a constructed-ix speech in these languages requires the translation of words from one language to other, and the transition from the perspective of one language to the other point of view.

For a clear separation of linguistic consciousness need a picture of the totality of the values of each language category, in which the characteristic features of the linguistic values appear visibly and clearly - they are regulatory constraints, the selectivity (for each position and only one strictly defined) and mandatory-ness of this choice. This discrepancy between the content and the nature of cognitive and linguistic reflection distinguishes even separate value of the cognitive representation or conception of the same object extra linguistic reality. The cognitive reflection of the element associated with the other parties to the same object or objects and freely complemented their earlier left out properties. A reflection in language, in the sense, it is associated with the interests of impact of the listener in a certain coverage of these objects, and any other of their coverage only hurt to the main purpose of speech. Cognitive and linguistic reflection included in different systems: in one case - in the relationships between things; in the other - in the relationships between people.

As a special language reflect the value of the semantic aspect of a separate formal language structure medium link between sign language (formal structure) and the same part of the extra-linguistic reality that this symbol represents. The relationship between the linguistic sign and the object is mediated by value, a sign

language - is not a sign, not a symbol and not a signal extra-linguistic object, the means of its message. Even the original name of the individual subject, accompanied by a pointing gesture, presents not a sound link to this object, but the act of allocating a clear picture of the object as its value. In the future, this initial "visual value" of the linguistic sign (the title) is activated in a situation with other objects with same function in a variety of relationships with them and increasingly loses its clarity and the apparent position of an intermediary, but even more so in real allegedly mediating function. And as a direct link between the sign and its object is not present, it's the straightforward.

This invisible, actually linguistic meaning) cannot be properly understand the language nor reasonable to construct it in a foreign language.

Accounting for the specifics of linguistic meanings implies clears the differences of linguistic and cognitive awareness. Last one is the product knowledge of things (better to say - objects), what can be, in particular, and the language itself, and serves as a tool that helps navigate in things. Knowledge of a foreign language is an indicator of readiness for the implementation of professional activities within, not only his country, but also in other states, as a partnership with foreign countries more and more part of our lives. We can trace this trend on the example of the requirements for applicants for a particular position: at each case it contains the column "Languages", and sometimes employers are asked to send your CV in two versions: English and Russian. Based on the foregoing, it is difficult not to conclude that a foreign language has long and firmly entered the life of the modern educated person. Furthermore, it should take it to account the processes in the field of education at international level. Speaking about this, I mean "unification of Europe into a single economic space, which led to a formation and a single European Higher Education Area" (Bolon Declaration, 1999), which was reflected in the so-called Bologna process, which began in 1999. The innovative development of Russian education is currently underway with a view of it, so staff of universities has begun

to implement a new paradigm of higher education, aimed at training specialists in accordance with the requirements of the XXI century.

New goals and objectives of higher education are reflected in inter-national and national documents and, in general, can be summarized as follows:

- Development of culture of the person, understood in the broadest sense of the word - from culture to culture of speech mechanism of communication;
- Implementation of creative potential of the individual learner's means of developing awareness of their own responsibility for the selection of objectives, methods and pace of their training in high school;
 - Formation of the needs of self, understanding of non-need for continuous replenishment of the autonomous knowledge and its application in power dictate the information revolution;
- organization of training on an interactive basis.

The above regulations fixed in the new concept of foreign language in not language high school education, which states that "a foreign language is an integral component of the pro-modern specialist professional training of any profile". In order to clarify this situation in the state educational standards of higher professional education emphasizes that graduate "should possess the professional competence in the translation of the original technical literature on the specialty, in lectures and presentations, writing scientific articles in foreign language" and must be "able to continue education and training activities in the foreign language environment".

In accordance with the contents of these areas are developed as the final requirements for the students at the end of their education.

- be skilled in colloquial everyday speech (the normative pronunciation and the rhythm of speech and use them in present communication);
- understand spoken (monologue and dialogue) it on every day and special topics;
- Actively wield the most common (base) program and basic grammatical phenomena for professional speech;

- know the basic vocabulary of a common language, vocabulary, representing neutral scientific style, as well as basic terminology of its wide and narrow specialty
- Read and understand the dictionary books on a wide and narrow profile of the specialty;
- know the basics of public speaking - making posts, pre-clade (with preparation);
- To participate in the discussion of topics related to the profession (to ask questions and answer questions);

The advantage of the cognitive mind is that it is true, verifiable practice, systematic effect on things and measure its actual result matches the expected. Free from immediate needs, but providing for the use of a variety of cognitive consciousness tends to reflect the completeness of its facilities and is open to additions and even applications.

Today there are many different methods and ways of teaching a foreign language, as well as a huge range of benefits, the choice of which depends only on your preferences, tastes and fantasies. One of the most effective and interesting way to learn English, in my opinion, is to read English newspapers. In fact, reading about foreign periodical benefits can talk endlessly. They not only keep abreast of all the latest news and events in the world, but also help to expand vocabulary, improve grammar and writing. But most importantly, they contribute to the development of language skills, creating their own style and manner of speech. I also, as a teacher with years of experience, I can safely say that newspapers have one major advantage over the various aids and textbooks - is a "living" language, the language, using which, you will not look ridiculous and absurd among its speakers. Furthermore, as practice shows, the use of newspapers and magazines in the classroom - it is a very exciting process, which encourages students to constantly improve their knowledge of a foreign language. A variety of newspapers and magazines allows you to engage with students of different levels of knowledge of a foreign language, and a variety of articles able to meet the students a wide variety of interests and tastes.

The important role played by the fact that now almost any foreign periodicals can be found on the Internet, and even living in a distant Russian province, you can read the latest edition of the British or American, and also free of charge. Based on my experience, the newspaper article - it's a huge number of interesting jobs, which are sure to enjoy both teachers and students. One of my favorite is called the "Title / Headline», when students only on the title you need to guess what was going on in the article and try to tell her. The same exercise can be done on key phrases or sentences, the isolation of the article. Thus, students expand vocabulary, improve their oral communication skills and develop their imagination, which is also important in the learning process. In practicing certain phrases and designs can be a little "gossip" about famous people, or about some scandalous incident. A useful phrase like: —Have you heard about ...», —Did you know that ...? —, —Guess what ... —or phrases to answer? — Really? I do not believe it», —Are you joking», —How / when did it happen». At the end of XX - beginning of XXI century was the development of professionally-oriented languages due to the evolution of science, industry and society as a whole. New approaches to teaching foreign languages contributed to the Council of Europe - the organization responsible for cultural and fruitful cooperation of European countries, which recommends to organize the training with knowledge of a foreign language at a functional level, taking into account the specific specialty and the conditions in which it is supposed to use the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

Grammar also will not stand aside. Depending on the knowledge of grammatical material, it is possible to carry out tasks of varying complexity, for example, to make interrogative sentences on the subject or to find verbs, after which used the gerund / infinitive with to / not to. Of course, learning any foreign language, first of all, you need to find a good professional, reliable and trustworthy mentor who will guide you right to the target. The success in the study of any subject is impossible without serious self-study. To cite an example: "In the development of the mother tongue a

hundred times the child hears and speaks a word, repeating it in different grammatical forms, before it finally becomes an integral part of its vocabulary. When learning a foreign language a person does the same thing: coaching pronunciation, repeating the words, Sun-produces in the memory means the connections between them, that is, memory circuits constructing sentences. The highest productivity of such work provides a "tandem" lesson - independent work. This lesson can be compared with data entry and independent work with their reproduction ". Consequently, for the teacher in the planning of the learning process it is very important to clearly define the content ratio of components of the tandem: what material is to give the students in class, and some as homework.

And so in each case their application language consciousness with respect to extra-linguistic reality is the system is closed, normative for all mandatory and univocal. Each natural language only in so far as open to new means of verbal communication, new regulations in which it enhances the possibility of communication and leadership behavior with the help of speech. Language consciousness is a form of co-public knowledge, and as it is not something new.

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